

AN AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF VATAJA GULMA W.S.R. TO CHRONIC TROPICAL CALCIFIC PANCREATITIS – A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Gulma is one among the *ashta mahagada* mainly occurring due to aggravated *vata dosha*. It covers various gastrointestinal and gynaecological disease occurring in *Mahasrothas* presenting with *shoola* and *shotha*. Any type of pain with palpable mass in any quadrant of abdomen can be considered as *Gulma*. Pancreatitis is an inflammation of the pancreas caused by premature activation of digestive enzymes leading to autodigestion of pancreatic tissue. A male patient of age 21 years complains of recurrent pain in abdomen of hard stools was treated with oral medicine for first 5 days, followed by *Abhyanga*, *Swedana* and *Basti karma* along with oral medicine for 8 days. Patient got significant improvement from pain as well as other symptoms after the course of treatment.

KEYWORDS: *Gulma*, pancreatitis, *mahasrothas*, *rooksha*, tight junctions, *vega dharana*, *basti*, *koshtagata vata*.

INTRODUCTION

Gulma is *vatapradhana*, *tridoshaja vyadhi* occur mainly in 5 different *sthanas*. *Gulma* is named because of its *pindakara*,^[1] *sparshopalabya* as well as *paripinditawa*.^[2] It is characterised mainly by *shoola* and *shotha*.^[3] Chronic inflammation in pancreas is pancreatitis. The major symptoms include pain in abdomen, constipation or oil mixed stools, loss of weight, indigestion etc. The symptoms of chronic pancreatitis can be correlated with *vataja gulma*.

CHIEF COMPLAINTS

A 21-year-old male patient complains of recurrent pain in abdomen which radiates to right lower back since the last 8 years, but aggravated in the last 1 week and complains of hard stools for the last 2-3 years approached the OPD of Panchakarma.

ASSOCIATED COMPLAINTS

Complaints of indigestion, reduced appetite, and dissatisfaction after food for 2-3 years and Distention of abdomen, occasionally, for 2-3 years.

HISTORY OF PRESENT ILLNESS

Patient was apparently healthy before 2017. In 2017, patient had typhoid fever and was treated. Two weeks later, in September 2017, one fine early morning, patient suddenly had severe abdominal pain which was of piercing type along with 3-4 episodes of vomiting and nausea. Patient was taken to a nearby hospital and treated with IV fluids, antibiotic and antacid injections. 2 months later (in November 2017), one morning he had severe abdominal pain which was continuous and intolerable. Patient could not find any relief in any position or movements including sitting or standing.

Patient was vomiting 2-3 times and had multiple episodes of loose stools (6-10) for which they advised MRCP, which revealed acute pancreatitis. Later in 2018 June, patient had severe abdominal pain which was dull aching and was radiating to the right side of lumbar region with a little relief by bending forward, associated with increased frequency of passing stools after the previous day's dinner, for which he took treatment and got discharged. In 2022 as well, he had similar episodes, but he managed the condition. In the end of 2024, patient had severe aching pain, which was radiating toward right lower back side, which made him to bend forward. Besides, he had vomiting and other symptoms similar to the last episode of pain. Hence, patient took consultation in BGS Medical college and hospital, Nagarur. He underwent CT scan and was provisionally diagnosed with chronic pancreatitis and was treated for the same. After treatment, he had improvement in pain, but other symptoms were persisting.

In January of 2025, he had sudden onset of pain in abdomen, which was dull aching, and continuous which made him to bend forward. He also complained of passing hard stools once in 2-3 days, associated with indigestion, occasional gurgling sound in abdomen, reduced appetite and dissatisfaction after food along with reduction in weight (~6-8kg). Hence, for the above complaints he approached the OPD of Panchakarma in SKAMCH & RC for better management.

PAST HISTORY

H/O Typhoid fever 8 years back.

N/K/C/O – HTN/ DM/ Thyroid Dysfunction/ Dyslipidaemia

FAMILY HISTORY

Mother is a K/C/O Hypertension in the past 20 years and DM TYPE 2 since 15 years.

VAYAKTIKA VRUTTANTA

Diet – Mixed (Non-Veg – Once in 15 days)

Appetite – Reduced, 2 times/day (less quantity) – not feeling satisfaction

Bowel – Constipated (once in 2-3 days) since 2-3 years

Bristol stool – Grade - 2

Sleep – Disturbed

Micturition – 1-2 times/day,

Night – 1 time (not regularly)

Habits: No habits of alcohol and smoking

Tea / coffee: 1-2 times/ day

GENERAL EXAMINATION

Decubitus	– Sitting
Built	– Moderate
Nourishment	– Moderate
Pallor	– Absent
Icterus	– Absent
Cyanosis	– Absent
Koilonychia	– Absent
Lymphadenopathy	– Absent

Edema	– Absent
Temperature	– 98° F (afebrile)
Pulse	– 68 bpm
BP	– 120/70 mm hg
RR	– 18 cpm
Height	– 170 cm
Weight	– 50 kg

ASHTASTHANA PAREEKSHA

Nadi	– Vata Pitta
Mutra	– 1-2 times / day, 1 in Night (Not regularly)
Mala	– Constipated (once in 2-3 days)
Jihwa	– Lipta
Shabdha	– Prakruta
Sparsha	– Anushna sheeta
Druk	– Prakruta
Aakriti	– Madhyama

DASHAVIDHA PAREEKSHA

Prakruthi	– Vata-Pittaja	
Vikruthi:		
Hetu	– Aharaja	: Rooksha Ahara, Vishamashana, Refrigerated food items.
	– Viharaja	: Vegadharana, long improper standing postures
Dosha	– Vata Pradhana Tridosha	
Dushya	– Rasa, Raktha	
Desha	– Sadharana	
Bala	– Madhyama	
Sara	– Madhyama	
Samhanana	– Madhyama	
Pramana	– Madhyama	
Satmya	– Vyamishra Satmya	
Satva	– Madhyama	

Ahara Shakti

Abhyavarana Shakti	– Avara
Jarana Shakti	– Avara
Vyayama Shakti	– Avara
Vaya	– Yauvana

SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION

1. Respiratory System Examination

Inspection:	Shape of chest – normal and bilaterally Symmetrical, Symmetrical expansion of chest noted. Abdomino-thoracic breathing pattern noted.
Palpation:	Position of trachea – centrally placed.
Percussion:	Resonant over the lung field except cardiac dullness
Auscultation:	Normal vesicular breath sounds heard.

2. Cardiovascular System Examination

Inspection:	Chest – Bilaterally symmetrical, No scar marks
Palpation:	Apex beat felt at left 5 th intercostal space medial to mid-clavicular line
Percussion:	Cardiac dullness in 4 th , 5 th inter costal spaces.
Auscultation:	S1, S2 heard, No murmurs. Heart rate - 68bpm.

3. CNS Examination

Alert and orientation: Present
 Memory: Intact
 All cranial nerves intact
 Muscle atrophy: Absent
 Muscle tone: Normotonic
 Muscle power - Normal [5/5]
 Pain, pressure, temperature – Intact
 Deep tendon reflexes – Normal [2+]

4. Integumentary System

Skin colour – Chest, Abdomen, face, upper & lower limbs – No Discoloration
 Nails – Normal
 Itching – Absent
 Discharge – Absent

5. Musculoskeletal System Examination

Gait - Normal.
 Inspection of joints and spine- NAD
 Palpation - NAD
 ROM of all joints - Possible, no painful/restricted movements.

6. Git System

Lips: Cracks, Fissure, Cheilitis, Ulcer – Absent
 Gums: Recession, Gingivostomatitis, Bleeding – Absent
 Teeth: Tartar, Stain, Fluorosis – Absent
 Tongue: Coating, Fissure/furrowing, Ulcers – Absent
 Buccal mucosa & palate: ulcers – Absent
 Abdomen: No scar marks & dilated veins & discoloration.
 Contour & shape of abdomen - Mildly distended
 Umbilicus: centrally placed & inverted

7. Special signs

1. Cullens sign – Absent
2. Fox sign – Absent
3. Korte's sign – Positive
4. Grunwald sign – Absent
5. Grey turners sign – Absent
6. Kamenchik's sign – Positive

Palpation: Tenderness present over Right hypochondrium, Epigastric, left hypochondrium, right lumbar & Umbilicus
 Organomegaly, Rebound tenderness, Guarding, rigidity, Fluid thrill – Absent
 Percussion: Tympanic over abdomen, Dullness in liver.

Auscultation: Bowel sounds heard.

Samprapti Ghatakas

Dosha – Vata pradhana tridosha vyadhi
Dushya – Rasa, Raktha
Agni – Jatharagni
Srotas – Rasavaha, Annavaha, Purishavaka
Sroto dushti lakshana – Sanga, Vimarga gamana
Udbhavasthana – Koshta
Sanchara sthana – Mahasrothas
Vyakta sthana – Hridaya, Nabhi, Basti, Parshwa
Rogamarga – Abhyantara
Vyadhi swabhava – Chirakari
Sadhya asadhyata – Utkrishta

Roga Pareeksha

1. *Nidana* – Vishama ashana, Rooksha aharas, refrigerated food items, Vegadharana – vata, mutra (occasionally), long improper standing postures
2. *Poorva roopa* – Vibhandha, Agni vaishamya, Atopa
3. *Roopa* – Vitsanga, Anaha, Kukshi-parshwa ruja
Upashaya – Bending forward position, Medication
Anupashaya – Nothing specific

Samprapthi

Because of *Ashuchi* / *Binnamaryadha* / *Kshatha* / *Akshatha* patient had typhoid fever which can be interpreted as *Bhoothabishanka vishama jwara*. There is a mechanism called bacterial translocation, from intestine. At the same time because of the *jwara*, there is increase of *rookshatha* in the body [4] further leads to *karshanene karshiitha* and ends up in *vataprakopa*. Similarly, when *vata prakruthi* person indulges in *Nidanas* like *atirooksha*, *vishamashana*, *vegadharana* etc. further leads to *vata prakopa* in *koshta*. Together these lead to *margavarana* by *kapha* and *pitta* and enters to *mahasrothas*. Then, it will obstruct the *urdwa* and *adho marga* finally leads to *shoolam upajayathe* in *hridaya*, *parshwa*, and *basti*. which is one component in *gulma*.

INVESTIGATION

Ultrasonography of abdomen

FINAL DIAGNOSIS

Apakwa, *Antarhata*, *Vataja Gulma*/ Stage A- Chronic tropical calcified Pancreatitis.

Table 1: Therapeutic Intervention.

Days	Oral medicine/ treatments	Observation
Phase 1 5 days	1) Tab. <i>Suvarna Sutasekhara Rasa</i> 1-0-1 (A/F) 2) Tab. <i>Maha shanka vati</i> 1-0-1 (A/F) 3) <i>Sariva kalpa</i> 3tsp-3tsp-3tsp (A/F)	1) Pain in abdomen reduced by 20% and radiating pain to lower back still persisting 2) Nauseating feeling reduced. 3) Appetite – Not improved 4) Stool hardness – Persisting
Phase 2 8 days	1) <i>Sarvanga abhyanga</i> with <i>moorchita taila</i> . 2) <i>Sarvanga parisheka</i> with <i>dashamoola qwatha</i>	1) Pain in abdomen reduced by 70-80 % and radiating pain absent.

	3) <i>Yastimadhu ksheera yoga basti Anuvasana</i> <i>Sukumara ghrta</i> = 80ml Niruha Honey - 60 ml <i>Saindhava lavana</i> - 6 gms <i>Sukumara ghrta</i> – 100 ml <i>Yastimadhu kalka</i> – 30 gms <i>Yastimadhu ksheerapaka</i> – 350ml	2) Nauseating feeling – Not persisting. 3) Appetite and digestion – improved 4) Passing stools daily.																
	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td><td>2</td><td>3</td><td>4</td><td>5</td><td>6</td><td>7</td><td>8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>A</td><td>N</td><td>A</td><td>N</td><td>A</td><td>N</td><td>A</td><td>A</td> </tr> </table>	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	A	N	A	N	A	N	A	A	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8											
A	N	A	N	A	N	A	A											
Advice on discharge For 15 days	Tab. <i>Suvarna sutasekhara rasa</i> 1-0-1 (After food) Tab. <i>Maha shanka vati</i> 1-0-1 (After food) <i>Sariva kalpa</i> 3tsp-3tsp-3tsp (After food)	Follow up after 15 days 20% pain persisting in initial 4 days after discharge. Thereafter, no pain. Patient started gaining weight. Appetite – Good Bowel – Hard, passing daily No abdominal distention																

Figure 1: VAS Assessment.

DISCUSSION

In *Gulma vyadhi*, *mahasrothas*, *rooksha* and *katina* plays an important role. Here *mahasrothas* is *koshta*. *Rooksha* can be understood as tight junction and *katina* is the type of inflammation.

Tight junctions^[5] are the specialised structures that form a barrier between epithelial or endothelial tissue. It prevents the leakage of substances, selective permeability and signal regulation. Claudines and occludines are the major proteins involved in maintaining the integrity. Because of the disruption in tight junction and translocation mechanism there is manifestation of disease. The same concept can be understood in ayurveda also as *kapha* has the property of *shlish alingane* which means keep together or adhere together similar to tight junction. So, the disruption leads to *snehadi guna shoonyatha* in *mahasrothas* and leads to increase of *rooksha* there by manifestation of disease.

Role of *vegadharana*

Gulma is a *vyadhi* that can be manifest because of *vata* and *mutra vegadharana*. The concepts of *vegadharana* can be understood under the umbrella of ganglia.^[6] Ganglia are broadly classified into parasympathetic ganglia and sympathetic ganglia. Para sympathetic is situated near or within the target organ. Whereas

sympathetic is apart from target organ. It acts as relay station where information is processed and transmitted between different part of nervous system. In general, *vegadhara* effects the parasympathetic ganglia leads to disruption, further leads to target organ failure or *vyadhi* leads to *vyadhi*. The same can be applied here as well and is because of *vegadharana*, over activation of parasympathetic enteric ganglia in pancreas, increased enzyme secretion further leads to immune system activation, autodigestion and manifestation of pain further leads to pancreatitis.

CHIKITSA

The *chikitsa sutra* of *gulma* emphasis *snigdha bhojana*, *abhyanga*, *snehapana*, *niruha*, *anuvasana basti* and *swedana karma*.^[7] Here, treatment in the form of *abhyanga*, *swedana*, and *basti* was adopted along with the oral medicines.

Rationality behind usage of oral medicine

Here, the *vata* in the *koshta* is vitiated and leads to manifest of symptoms like *mootra varcha nigraha* and *gulma* ^[8] which was present in the patient. *Gulma* is nothing but *shotha* and *shoola* anywhere in *mahasrothas*. So, the line of management for *koshta gata vata* is *ksharam pibet narah*, *Deepana* and *pachana*. To achieve the action, *Suvarna sutasekhara rasa*, which is

mentioned *bhaishajya ratnavali*, *Maha shanka vati* which is mentioned in *Bharata bhaishajya ratnavali* 5th volume and *sariva kalpa* was advised. The above 2 tablets contain *kshara*, *amla dravyas*, *lavana*, and *hingu* etc. hence it will help in this condition. *Sariva kalpa* is used to subside the *pitta* in the *koshtha*.

Role of *Abhyanga*

In the *Poorva karma* of *Basti*, *Abhyanga* followed by *Swedana karma* to the entire body is emphasized. Here, *Sarvanga Abhyanga* followed by *sarvanga parisheka* was therefore adopted. This helps in *draveekarana* of *malas*, just like a cloth soaked in water mixed with dye sucks up the pigments. Similarly, from the body the *basti* absorbs and eliminates the *doshas*.^[9] *Abhyanga* stimulates low threshold mechano-receptors, such as Ruffini endings, and rapidly adapting Pacinian corpuscles. These are connected to alpha beta fibres which are large, myelinated, fast conducting fibres responsible for touch and pressure. They activate inhibitory interneurons in substantia gelatinosa and releases Enkephalins. This leads to hyper polarisation and inhibits substance P. *Abhyanga* helps in release of serotonin, endorphin and dopamine which helps in pain reduction by inhibiting substance P.

Role of *Swedana*

Here, *swedana* in the form of *parisheka* was adopted. As *pitta sthana* along with *vata dosha* is involved, *parisheka* will be beneficial. *Swedana* after *snehana* helps in pacification of *vata dosha*.^[10] The combined effect of *snehana* and *swedana* helps in attaining *mardavata* to *srothas*, helps in pacification of *vata*, thus clearing the obstruction and therefore helps in managing *gulma*. To subside *shoola*, bloating and constipation in *vataja Gulma swedana* in the form of *nadi sweda*, *prasthara* and *Sankara sweda* can be adopted.^[11]

Role of *Basti*

Basti can be advised for all type of *vyadhi* due to *vata* origin. It can be considered as *ardha chikitsa* as well. Both *niruha* and *anuvasana basti* is highlighted as main treatment in *vataja gulma*. Apart from that while explaining *pathya* for *gulma basti* has been emphasized. Here, *basti* in the form of *yastimadhu ksheera basti* has been used. In general, *basti* helps in pacification *vata dosha* and *yastimadhu* and *ksheera* helps to pacify the *pitta dosha*. Here, *sukumara grita* is used for both *anuvasana* and *niruha basti*. It is a *yamaka Sneha*, it contains both *go grita* as well as *eranda taila*. *Yamaka Sneha* is beneficial in chronic pain or *vata* predominant conditions. It also enhances the therapeutic efficacy. *Sukumara grita* acts as *vatanulomaka*, *mruvu rechaka*, helps for *deepama* as well as *pachana* and *bruhmana*.

Niruha Basti is a hyper osmotic solution that causes movement of solvent from cells of colon to the lumen containing *Basti Dravya*. This facilitates the detoxification of endotoxins there by helping in colon cleansing. System biology explains that all the organs are

interconnected at the molecular level. Any molecular incident occurs at the cellular level, then at the tissue level and ultimately at the organ level. Altering the pathophysiology at one level, results in changes in pathophysiology at another level. *Basti* administration induces changes at the lower gut, specifically the luminal epithelium. This, in turn, influences the entire gastro-intestinal tract and vital organs such as liver, pancreas, gall bladder and spleen. These, in turn, modulate the activity of interconnected systems including the renal, respiratory, circulatory and integumentary systems, ultimately resulting in systemic changes throughout the body. The classical references state that *Basti* eliminates *doshas* lodged from the soles to the crown (*Apada-Talamurdha*). Thus, *Basti* exerts its therapeutic effects across multiple levels.^[12]

CONCLUSION

Shoola and *shotha* are the typical feature of *gulma*, which is happening anywhere in gastro-intestinal tract. *Chikitsa* is that which does *samprapthi vighatana*. Here, this was achieved through oral medicines, *snehana*, *swedana* and *basti karma*. This single case study shows significant effect through *shamana* and *shodhana*, which are the basic principles of ayurveda. Thus, ayurvedic line of management can be implemented in treating chronic pancreatitis with calcification during attacks and as well as to prevent the complication like type 3C diabetes and steatorrhea. This case study may provide as a model for further researchers.

REFERENCES

1. Agnivesha, Charaka, Dridhabala, Chakrapanidatta. Nidanasthana Chapter 3 Verse 7. In: Acharya Y T (Edi.). Charaka Samhita Ayurveda Deepika Commentary. Reprint Edition 2021. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, p.209.
2. Agnivesha, Charaka, Dridhabala, Chakrapanidatta. Chikitsasthana Chapter 5 Verse 7. In: Acharya Y T (Edi.). Charaka Samhita Ayurveda Deepika Commentary. Reprint Edition 2021. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, p.435.
3. Agnivesha, Charaka, Dridhabala, Chakrapanidatta. Sutrasthana Chapter 18 Verse 29. In: Acharya Y T (Edi.). Charaka Samhita Ayurveda Deepika Commentary. Reprint Edition 2021. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, p.107.
4. Agnivesha, Charaka, Dridhabala, Chakrapanidatta. Chikitsasthana Chapter 3 Verse 216, 217. In: Acharya Y T (Edi.). Charaka Samhita Ayurveda Deepika Commentary. Reprint Edition 2021. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, p.418.
5. Citi S, Fromm M, Furuse M, González-Mariscal L, Nusrat A, Tsukita S, Turner JR. A short guide to the tight junction. J Cell Sci., 2024 May 1; 137(9): jcs261776. doi: 10.1242/jcs.261776. Epub 2024 May 7. PMID: 38712627; PMCID: PMC11128289. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11128289/>
6. Waxenbaum JA, Reddy V, Varacallo MA. Anatomy,

- Autonomic Nervous System. [Updated 2023 Jul 24]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK539845>.
7. Agnivesha, Charaka, Dridhabala, Chakrapanidatta. Chikitsasthana Chapter 5 Verse 22. In: Acharya Y T (Edi.). Charaka Samhita Ayurveda Deepika Commentary. Reprint Edition 2021. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, p.437.
 8. Agnivesha, Charaka, Dridhabala, Chakrapanidatta. Chikitsasthana Chapter 28 Verse 24. In: Acharya Y T (Edi.). Charaka Samhita Ayurveda Deepika Commentary. Reprint Edition 2021. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, p.617.
 9. Agnivesha, Charaka, Drudabala, Chakrapanidatta. Sidhi Sthana, Chapter 7, Verse.65. In: Acharya YT (Edi.), Ayurveda Deepika Commentary on Charaka Samhita. Reprint Edition: 2019. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Orientalia, 2019; p.712.
 10. Kaviraj Shri Govinda Das Sen, 32th Chapter , Verse 5-6 In: Prof. Siddhi Nandan Mishra (Edi.), Bhaishajya Ratnavali with Siddiprada Hindi Commentary. Reprint Edition: 2015. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashan.p.206.
 11. Agnivesha, Charaka, Dridhabala, Chakrapanidatta. Chikitsasthana Chapter 5 Verse 99,100. In: Acharya Y T (Edi.). Charaka Samhita Ayurveda Deepika Commentary. Reprint Edition 2021. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, p.441.
 12. Shukla GD, Pandey S, Thakar AB. Pharmacodynamic understanding of Basti: A contemporary approach. International Journal of Pharmaceutical Biological science Archive. 2012 [Internet], [cited 2025 June 10]; 3(4): 893–6. Available from: <https://ijpba.info/index.php/ijpba/article/view/758/519>.